

DACEM

Digitising Academic Catalogues for Enhanced Mobility

WP 2. Course Catalogues mapping and technical state of the art
at European HEIs

Focus Groups and Interviews Final Report

Elaborated by
Tallinn University, Estonia

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1. Introduction

This report consolidates the findings from the interviews and focus group discussions conducted as part of the DACEM project, which aimed to explore the experiences and challenges faced by international students in relation to course catalogs and mobility systems. The report incorporates data from 9 partners, providing a comprehensive overview of student feedback, staff insights, and system functionality across different universities.

Through the DACEM project, a total of **230** individuals were involved in the research activities, including international student exchange coordinators, Erasmus+ staff, and international students. The data was gathered from May to October 2024, and the findings focus on key areas such as catalog usability, accessibility, student satisfaction, and areas for improvement. By analyzing these shared experiences, this report aims to inform future developments in course catalog systems and international student mobility frameworks, ultimately enhancing the student experience and ensuring smoother exchanges between universities.

2. Methodology

This research utilized a combination of interviews and focus groups to assess the current state of online Course Catalogs (CCs) and gather insights from key stakeholders.

2.1 Interviews with Erasmus+ Coordinators and Staff

Interviews were conducted with university staff, including Erasmus+ coordinators and those responsible for managing course catalogs and student mobility. The goal was to understand their experiences with the current CC system, challenges in updating and maintaining information, and needs for improvement. The interview questions focused on the usability of CCs, issues with outdated or inaccurate information, and the functionalities required to enhance the system.

2.2 (Focus group) Interviews with International Students

Focus groups were held with international students, including those participating in Erasmus mobility programs, to gather feedback on their experiences using the course catalog. Discussions explored challenges in accessing and navigating course information, preferred features, and ideas for improvements. Students provided input on how the CC can be made more user-friendly, including preferences for search functionality and mobile accessibility.

2.3 Data Collection Timeline

The data collection was spread over an extended period as the original timeline was overlapping with summer holidays making the interviews challenging. Therefore partners decided to expand the data collection period into the fall semester of 2024. Each session

was carefully scheduled to ensure representation from staff and students across all partner universities. Data analysis occurred after all interviews and focus groups were completed, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the current issues and requirements for CC systems.

3. Key Findings

3.1. Challenges with Course Catalogs

One of the primary challenges identified is the lack of updated and accurate information in many course catalogs. Students and staff frequently report encountering outdated descriptions, creating uncertainty during the application process and course selection. This issue is compounded by asynchronous timelines between catalog updates and mobility application deadlines. The limited level of detail in course descriptions further complicates the decision-making process, as students often lack critical information about course goals, learning outcomes, prerequisites, and assessment methods.

Inconsistencies in the structure and layout of CCs across institutions also pose significant challenges. Differences in formatting, categorization, and terminology make it difficult for students to compare offerings across universities. For instance, while some catalogs organize courses by faculty, others use study fields, leading to confusion and inefficiencies. Furthermore, the absence of clear indications regarding which courses are open to Erasmus+ students exacerbates the complexity of navigating these systems.

The lack of effective search and filtering functionalities further limits the usability of many CCs. Students often struggle to locate courses that match their academic needs or language preferences due to rudimentary or non-intuitive search tools. Problems such as incomplete tagging, insufficient filtering options, and poorly designed navigation exacerbate this issue, requiring users to invest significant time and effort in identifying suitable courses.

3.2. Positive Aspects and Functional Features

Despite the challenges, several course catalogs demonstrate valuable features that improve the user experience. The integration of search functions and filters, where available, has been well-received by students and staff. Some catalogs allow filtering by language of instruction, study level, and semester, enabling users to narrow down their options effectively. Advanced systems also feature direct links to detailed faculty pages or course registration platforms, ensuring seamless navigation and access to relevant information.

The inclusion of interactive features and media has been noted as a positive trend. Virtual tours, campus maps, and videos detailing course content enhance the overall user experience, particularly for students unfamiliar with the institution. Similarly, systems that offer multi-lingual support cater effectively to the diverse needs of international students.

Several universities have also prioritized the integration of course catalogs with broader administrative systems, such as online learning agreements or enrollment tools. This functionality streamlines the mobility process, allowing students to explore course options and finalize their registrations within a unified platform.

3.3. Recommendations for Improvement

To address the challenges, course catalogs should prioritize comprehensive, accurate, and up-to-date information. Clear timelines and protocols for updating course details are essential to ensure that students rely on accurate content during critical decision-making periods. Incorporating detailed course descriptions that include prerequisites, assessment methods, schedules, and ECTS credits would provide students with a clearer understanding of their options.

Standardizing the structure and layout of CCs across institutions would significantly enhance usability. Adopting a unified format for categorizing courses by study field, academic level, and semester would allow students to compare offerings easily. Similarly, the inclusion of clear indications for Erasmus+ course eligibility would simplify navigation for mobility students.

Improving search and filtering functionalities should be a key focus area. Advanced filtering options that allow students to sort courses by study level, language, faculty, and availability would make CCs more user-friendly. Additionally, integrating AI-driven virtual assistants or chatbots could assist users in navigating the system and finding relevant courses more efficiently.

3.4. Usability and Accessibility

User feedback highlights the importance of designing CCs with simplicity and intuitiveness in mind. A streamlined interface with a clean layout and logical navigation pathways would greatly enhance usability. Interactive features such as drop-down menus and collapsible sections can prevent information overload while maintaining accessibility.

Accessibility across devices is also critical. Many students rely heavily on smartphones for daily tasks, and mobile-friendly CCs can improve their experience by providing on-the-go access to course information. Ensuring compatibility with assistive technologies would also cater to students with disabilities, promoting inclusivity.

3.5. Information Accuracy

Maintaining accurate and current information is crucial for effective CCs. Universities should implement robust mechanisms for regular updates, including automated notifications for staff and a visible timestamp indicating the last revision date. Allowing users to report outdated or incorrect information through a feedback mechanism could further enhance data reliability.

Real-time updates on course availability, enrollment conditions, and curriculum changes would address a common pain point among students. Linking CCs to dynamic faculty pages or central university systems can facilitate this process, ensuring that students always have access to the most relevant information.

3.6. Mobile-Friendliness and Multimedia

The shift toward mobile-compatible CCs is essential in meeting the needs of modern students. A responsive design that adapts seamlessly to different screen sizes and operating systems would improve accessibility and convenience. Including visuals and multimedia content, such as videos, photos, and interactive maps, can enhance engagement and simplify complex information. These features are particularly valuable for courses involving practical or experiential components, as they provide students with a clearer understanding of what to expect

3.7. Language and Course Clarity

Multi-lingual support is indispensable for international students navigating CCs. Providing course descriptions in English alongside the primary language ensures inclusivity and accessibility. However, it is equally important to adhere to the declared language of instruction, preventing discrepancies between advertised and actual teaching languages.

Clarity in course descriptions is another critical area. Detailed explanations of course goals, content, and expected outcomes help students make informed decisions. Clearly stating assessment methods, prerequisites, and the availability of courses for mobility students further enhances transparency.

4. Partner Institutions Findings

Tallinn University

1. **Navigation Challenges:** Students and Erasmus+ coordinators faced difficulties in navigating course catalogs and university websites. The disorganization, especially in Southern European partner universities, led to frustration. Course information was often hard to find, and users encountered multiple platforms, which fragmented the experience.
2. **Outdated or Inaccurate Information:** Outdated or incorrect course details, such as old semester dates and course codes, were common. This caused confusion, particularly when courses listed in the catalog were not actually offered, impacting students' course selection process.
3. **Improvement Areas:**

- **Mobile-Friendliness:** A strong demand for mobile-responsive catalogs, as many students access them via smartphones.
 - **Search and Filtering Functionality:** Efficient search tools with keywords and better filtering options (e.g., academic year, course availability) were requested.
 - **Multimedia Content:** Including course videos, images, and testimonials was seen as valuable for improving engagement and providing better context for students.
 - **Clear Differentiation:** Better visual distinction between undergraduate and graduate courses was recommended to prevent confusion.
 - **Up-to-Date Information:** Ensuring catalogs are regularly updated, possibly through automatic reminders or audits, was a key improvement suggestion.
 - **Clearer Integration:** Better integration with other platforms, such as providing access to course details after application submission, was needed.
4. **Student Experience and Satisfaction:** While international students expressed frustration with the current catalog systems, they praised Erasmus+ support and some universities' course catalog systems, including Tallinn University's, which was appreciated for its clarity and organization. However, student satisfaction hinged on the accuracy, accessibility, and usability of the catalog.

University of Thessaly

1. **Current Catalog Satisfaction:** The course catalog at the University of Thessaly was generally satisfactory to students, academic coordinators, and Erasmus+ office professionals, despite its lack of interactivity. The main issue was the limited number of courses available, but overall, the existing catalog served its purpose for course matching between institutions.
2. **Centralized Organization and Presentation:** There is a strong need for a centralized approach to manage and present course information, ensuring easy access to course descriptions for all University of Thessaly offerings, particularly with an international audience in mind.
3. **Content Improvements:**
 - **Detailed Course Information:** The catalog should include comprehensive details such as course objectives, schedules, assessment formats, industry links, mentorship opportunities, and instructor profiles.
 - **Up-to-Date Content:** The catalog should be regularly updated to reflect real-time changes in course details such as lecture times and project deadlines.
 - **Additional Features:** Including videos about course activities, student feedback, and information on the recognition of courses (e.g., ECTS) would enhance the catalog.
4. **Functionality and User Interface:**

- **Improved Interface:** Enhancements to the catalog's interface are needed for better usability, including improved search functionality and categorization of courses.
 - **Interactivity:** The catalog should allow students to interact with the content based on preferences such as course characteristics or specializations.
 - **Support for Special Needs:** Ensuring that the catalog is accessible to students with disabilities is critical for inclusivity.
5. **Portability and Access:**
- **Mobile and Web Access:** A mobile-friendly version of the catalog, alongside a web-based interface, is essential for students accessing information from various devices.
6. **Broader Erasmus+ Support:**
- **Support for Practical Training:** Expanding Erasmus+ services to include students participating in practical training is recommended.
 - **Using the Catalog for Support Activities:** The catalog could be a tool for information days and other student support activities, further enhancing the Erasmus+ experience.

University of Vigo

1. **Current Course Catalog Issues:**
- **Outdated and Inaccurate Information:** There is a major concern about the lack of timely updates and accuracy of the information provided in the CC.
 - **Poor Functionality:** The current course catalog (CC) suffers from issues such as malfunctioning search features and scattered information across multiple platforms. These are persistent problems that need to be addressed for a more user-friendly experience.
2. **New Visions for the Role of the Course Catalog:**
- **Tool for Erasmus Coordinators:** The CC could be better utilized by Erasmus coordinators for preparing bilateral agreements and helping students identify potential destinations.
 - **Support for Teacher Mobility:** The CC could also serve as a resource for teachers to explore mobility opportunities, identifying courses and academic staff across institutions.
 - **Identifying Program Gaps:** Academic staff could use the CC to spot gaps in their own programs and consider alternative offerings or new courses in collaboration with industry representatives.
 - **Improving University Coordination:** The CC can be useful for teachers involved in new program development, ensuring compatibility across universities, particularly within the European University Alliances (EUA).
3. **Suggested Information Enhancements:**

- **Campus and Location Details:** Students desire clearer information about campus locations, especially for universities spread across multiple cities.
 - **Recognition and Grading Systems:** Clearer details on course recognition, including historic recognition examples and a comparison of grading systems between countries, would aid students in their decision-making.
 - **Living Conditions and Student Life:** Information about housing, local costs, public transport, and cultural events should be included to help students prepare for their stay.
 - **Student and Coordinator Connections:** Including contact details for Erasmus coordinators, along with opportunities to connect with past or current students, would enhance the experience.
4. **Non-Functional Requirements:**
- **Harmonization of Information:** The structure and content of CCs need to be more standardized across institutions to ensure consistency and ease of use.
 - **Mobile and Web Accessibility:** Many participants emphasized the importance of having CCs that are optimized for both mobile and web platforms, ensuring they are accessible at any time.
 - **Regular Updates:** A more transparent update system, including dates and validity periods for the data, is needed to avoid outdated information.
 - **Avoid Duplication:** Information should not be replicated across different platforms but linked to authoritative sources, ensuring accuracy and reducing redundancy.
5. **Functional Features:**
- **Enhanced Search and Browsing:** The catalog should include robust search functionalities, filters, and interactive features like chatbots or maps for easier navigation.
 - **Student Feedback and Reviews:** Allowing students to share their experiences, similar to a social network or feedback system, would provide prospective students with valuable insights from previous participants.
 - **Visuals and Multimedia:** While not universally required, some participants suggested the addition of multimedia content (e.g., videos or visuals) to enhance the user experience.

University of Orleans

1. Current System and Weaknesses:

- **Inadequate Search Engine:** The existing course catalog (CC) suffers from an inefficient search engine that doesn't support keyword searches effectively. Additionally, it lacks important filters, such as geographical location, language of instruction, or exam periods.

- **Lack of Comprehensive Information:** The information available in the catalog is overly basic, missing essential details required by European standards, such as ECTS credits and course syllabi.
- **Limited Scope:** Currently, the catalog only includes information about degree courses, not individual course details. Users—students and staff alike—expect more detailed information for better decision-making.
- **External Information Issues:** Some content relies on external websites, leading to outdated and unreliable information being included in the catalog.

2. Updating Challenges:

- **Regular Updates Needed:** Although degree programs are accredited for five years, some course details, such as timetables, need frequent updates. The current system does not ensure that information is consistently and promptly updated, causing frustration for both students and IRO (International Relations Office) staff.
- **Complexity Due to Multiple Processes:** The separation of administrative and pedagogical registration processes adds complexity, leading to confusion and wasted time for students trying to find accurate, up-to-date course information.

3. Impact on Mobility:

- **Wasted Time and Potential Cancellations:** Students often have to search through multiple websites or contact teaching staff to obtain information, leading to inefficiencies. In some cases, the lack of accessible, accurate course information results in the cancellation of mobility opportunities.

4. Future Course Catalog Features:

- **Improved Search and Filtering:** The updated course catalog should include a more sophisticated search engine that allows for filtering by criteria such as geographical location, language of instruction, and exam periods.
- **More Detailed and Specific Information:** The catalog should provide more detailed information, including syllabi, ECTS credits, and other specifics required by European mobility standards.
- **Interactivity and Multimedia:** The new system should feature promotional videos, visual aids, and a funnel model for accessing specific course details (e.g., instructor names, timetables).
- **Mobile-Friendliness and Interoperability:** The catalog should be optimized for mobile use and be compatible with other IT tools, making it more accessible for students. It should also include support for students with special needs ("dys" students) and provide information on the resources available to them.
- **Interactive Screens in Faculties:** To increase accessibility and usability, interactive screens could be set up in faculties to allow students and staff to quickly access course information.

These improvements aim to address the inefficiencies, lack of detail, and accessibility issues currently hindering the University of Orleans' course catalog, enhancing the mobility preparation process for students and staff.

European University Foundation

1. Improving the Online Course Catalogue for Mobility Students:

- The **DACEM project** underlines the need to transform the online course catalogue (CC) into a **one-stop shop** for all course-related information for mobility students. This would streamline the mobility process, providing students with all relevant course details in one place, thus reducing the need for additional support from staff. Students would be able to easily compare courses across universities, helping them choose mobility destinations based on how well the courses fit their academic needs.

2. Information to Be Included in the Course Catalogue: Several essential details should be included to enhance the functionality of the course catalogue:

- **Standardised Course Descriptions:** This would enable easy comparison between courses from different institutions.
- **Reading Materials:** Including reading materials would help students assess the compatibility of the course with their home institution's curriculum.
- **Assessment Methods:** Clear information on whether exams will be written or oral, including the dates, is crucial for students' planning.
- **Course Schedule:** Students should be able to view the class schedule to plan their academic week without overlaps.
- **Classroom Location:** Especially important for universities with multiple campuses.
- **Acceptance of Mobility Students:** Clear information on whether mobility students can enroll in the course.
- **Teacher Information:** Including the name and contact details of the instructor.
- **Application Process and Deadlines:** Clear guidelines on how to apply for the course as a mobility student.
- **Language of Instruction:** Indicating the language of the course is essential for students.

3. Non-Functional Features:

- **Updated Information:** Ensuring that course details are regularly updated is vital, as course catalogs are often updated asynchronously with mobility calendars, leaving students to rely on outdated information.
- **Harmonisation of Course Catalogues:** Standardising the format of course catalogs across European HEIs would make it easier for students to compare courses and mobility options. This would create a more cohesive European mobility experience.

- **Supporting Media Content:** Interactive guides (e.g., video tutorials) to help students navigate the course catalog would reduce reliance on staff and boost student independence.
 - **Mobile Accessibility:** A platform adapted for mobile use would increase accessibility, ensuring students can access information anytime, anywhere, even without a laptop.
4. **Functional Features:**
- **Search and Filtering:** A powerful, intuitive search function is critical for students to find relevant courses easily. This would be more effective when information is standardised across universities.
 - **Connection with University Registry System:** Linking the course catalogue to the university's central registration system would allow students to see real-time data on course availability and registration processes, improving their ability to manage their schedules.

These findings emphasize the need for a comprehensive, user-friendly, and updated online course catalogue that enhances the mobility experience for students, supports staff in providing accurate and timely information, and helps European universities harmonize their course offerings to create a more seamless international experience for all involved.

Charles University

1. **General Issues with Course Catalogues:**
 - The current course catalogues (CCs) are far from ideal, with several recurring problems. Common issues include poor search functionality, scattered information, and outdated or inaccurate data. The course catalogues also lack many features recommended in the **ECTS Users' Guide**, and these issues need to be addressed to ensure a more reliable and user-friendly system.
2. **Improvements Suggested by Focus Group Members:** While the feedback was generally positive, several improvements were suggested:
 - **Clear Information on Erasmus+ Eligibility:** CCs should clearly state which courses are available for Erasmus+ students and outline any conditions compared to degree students who follow specific study programmes.
 - **Enhanced Filtering Options:** Key filtering features should include the ability to filter courses by study field, rather than faculty, as departmental structures vary widely among universities. Additionally, there should be a filter for courses specifically available to Erasmus+ students.
 - **Guidelines for Erasmus+ Students:** Detailed instructions or guidelines on how to navigate the CC and choose appropriate courses for Erasmus+ students should be provided.
 - **Up-to-Date Information:** Clear rules for regular updates and a reliable process for keeping course information current should be implemented.

- **Links to University Websites:** Since each university has its own system for updating course offers, the CC should include links to the specific university website for more detailed information.
 - **Interdisciplinary Opportunities:** Many students prefer interdisciplinary studies, so the catalogue should allow students to select courses across different departments or faculties.
 - **Course Description Detail:** The course description should include not only basic content, but also detailed objectives, expected achievements, and information about the teaching methods used.
 - **Mobile Compatibility:** The course catalogue should be accessible across multiple devices, particularly smartphones, to accommodate students who may be using mobile devices to browse.
 - **Pre-application Access:** Students should have access to a complete and up-to-date course catalogue before applying for an Erasmus+ stay at a university, as the course offerings are a major factor in destination selection.
 - **Course Layout:** The CC layout should include a drop-down menu for easy navigation, rather than overwhelming users with too much information on one page at once.
 - **System Resilience:** The platform must be able to handle high traffic, particularly during peak periods when many students are searching for courses. Cybersecurity and system resilience are crucial for smooth operation.
3. **Suggested Information to Include in Course Catalogues:** The following detailed information should be included for each course:
- **Course Title:** The name of the course.
 - **Study Field:** The academic discipline or field of study.
 - **Course Provider:** The faculty or department offering the course.
 - **Study Cycle:** The level of study (Bachelor, Master, Ph.D.).
 - **Number of ECTS Credits:** The number of credits awarded for the course.
 - **Teacher's Name and Contact Information:** For direct communication.
 - **Semester:** Indicate if the course is offered in the winter, summer, or academic year.
 - **Prerequisites/Corequisites:** Whether there are any required or recommended courses that must be completed beforehand.
 - **Registration Period and Process:** Clear information on how and when to register, including whether registration is online or via email.
 - **Number of Available Spots:** Availability of places in the course.
 - **Course Description:** A detailed description broken into sections such as course content, main goals, and expected knowledge and skills gained.
 - **Syllabus:** A comprehensive syllabus outlining the course structure.
 - **Literature:** The mandatory and recommended reading for the course.

- **Attestation Type:** Information on how students can pass the course (e.g., written exam, project, etc.).
- **Language of Instruction:** The language in which the course is taught.
- **Attestation Conditions:** Specific conditions required to complete the course successfully (e.g., attendance, assignments).
- **Seminar or Lecture:** Whether the course consists of seminars, lectures, or a combination.
- **Student Feedback:** Reviews or feedback from previous students to provide insights into the course.
- **Guidelines for Using the Course Catalogue:** Instructions on how to effectively use the CC.

These findings highlight the importance of ensuring that course catalogues are comprehensive, accurate, user-friendly, and regularly updated. Additionally, they emphasize the need for cross-university standardisation to facilitate better mobility experiences for Erasmus+ students.

Virtual Campus, Portugal

1. Enhanced Information for Decision-Making:

- **Campus and Program Location Details:** CCs should include detailed descriptions of campuses, facilities, and nearby amenities. This includes maps, public transportation options, parking facilities, and local points of interest, which are essential for students' daily logistics, especially for those studying at universities with multiple campuses or in different cities.
- **Recognition of Studies:** CCs should provide transparent information about the process of credit transfer and recognition of coursework completed at other institutions. This could include historical data showing past successful credit transfers, helping to set clear expectations for future students and alleviate potential bureaucratic challenges.
- **Grading Systems:** Clear explanations of grading scales and equivalence charts between local and international grading systems should be included to help students understand their academic performance in a global context. This would reduce confusion and anxiety regarding grade conversions.

2. Comprehensive Resources and Services Information:

- **Student Life and Services:** CCs should extend beyond academic content to include information on student life, housing, cultural activities, daily living costs (food, transport, entertainment), and practical tips. A calendar of cultural events and local transportation details could ease students' transitions and improve their overall experience.
- **Profiles of Past and Current Students:** Including testimonials or profiles of current and past students can offer prospective students valuable insights into

the institution's academic and social environment, aiding them in making informed decisions. Creating a network for prospective students to contact alumni can enhance support and create a sense of community.

- **Erasmus Coordinator and Mobility Staff Contacts:** Contact information for Erasmus coordinators and relevant mobility staff should be readily available, enabling efficient communication and support for students throughout their application process, course selection, and integration into the host institution.

3. Non-Functional Requirements and Design Considerations:

- **Harmonisation and Standardisation:** Standardising the format and structure of course catalogues across different institutions is key for improving accessibility and comparison. This includes consistent terminology, course credit systems, and academic calendars to create a cohesive and clear user experience.
- **Up-to-Date and Accurate Information:** Regular updates to course catalogues are essential to maintain their reliability. Features allowing users to report outdated or incorrect information should be implemented to ensure the catalogues remain accurate and helpful.
- **Accessibility and Mobile Compatibility:** CCs must be accessible on a variety of devices, especially mobile phones and tablets. They should be designed to be responsive and user-friendly across all platforms, ensuring inclusivity for students with disabilities, with compatibility for assistive technologies.
- **Visuals and Multimedia Content:** Including multimedia elements like videos, images, and interactive content can enrich the CC experience, particularly in practical study programs. This can include virtual tours and interactive maps to illustrate complex information in a more engaging and understandable way.

4. Functional Features:

- **Search and Navigation Features:** CCs should offer advanced search functions with filters to help users sort information based on various criteria such as level of study, field of interest, language of instruction, etc. Integrating chatbots could provide instant answers to common questions, improving accessibility and user satisfaction.
- **Feedback and Review Mechanisms:** Allowing students to leave feedback and reviews on courses and programs can provide valuable insights for prospective students, while also creating a feedback loop for institutions to improve their offerings based on real user experiences.

These suggestions aim to transform course catalogues into more comprehensive, user-friendly, and transparent resources. By addressing these areas, course catalogues can significantly enhance the academic and social experience for students, helping institutions better support their international and domestic student populations.

University of Maribor

1. Accessibility and User Experience:

- **Mobile-Friendliness and Accessibility:** Students and coordinators highlight the importance of having a mobile-friendly course catalogue. Since students rely on smartphones for daily tasks, a responsive and accessible design that works well on various devices is crucial. Issues with navigating the current PDF format on mobile devices indicate the need for a more flexible, responsive design.
- **User Interface and Customization:** There is a preference for a simple, user-friendly interface that balances usability with functionality. Students and coordinators suggest adding features like advanced filtering options, interactive previews (e.g., videos, photos), personalized recommendations, and customizable dashboards to enhance engagement and user flexibility.
- **Multi-lingual Support:** Coordinators emphasized the need for multi-lingual support to accommodate international students, ensuring the catalogue is accessible to a global audience.

2. Non-Functional Features:

- **Accuracy and Currency of Information:** Ensuring that the course catalogue is constantly updated with real-time information, particularly about course availability, enrolment conditions, and curriculum changes, is essential. Coordinators stress that accurate and current data is critical for effective decision-making.
- **Unique Links and Easy Access:** Coordinators suggested providing unique links to individual courses and study programs for easier access and sharing, which would improve navigation and information sharing.

3. Content and Information Presentation:

- **Information to be Included in Course Catalogues:** The catalogue should include detailed information such as course locations, languages, available quotas, enrolment conditions, and additional literature. It is also recommended to provide information about upcoming semesters and potential changes within study programs to help students plan effectively.
- **Consistent Terminology and Structure:** Clear and consistent terminology (e.g., distinguishing between bachelor and master courses) and improved categorization (e.g., separating summer and winter courses) would streamline course presentation and make it easier for students to find relevant courses.
- **Enhanced Course Descriptions:** More detailed descriptions of each course, including specific enrolment conditions and additional literature, were suggested. Linking to faculty pages for real-time course updates instead of publishing static catalogues would keep students informed about course status.

4. Interactivity and Integration:

- **Interactive and Customisable Features:** Students suggested adding features to sort, pin courses, integrate schedules, and enable direct course registration from within the catalogue. Coordinators also supported integrating the course catalogue with platforms like EWP and OLA to streamline enrolment processes.
- **AI and Virtual Assistants:** Coordinators recommended incorporating AI chatbots to reduce communication burdens and assist students through the application and course selection processes.

5. Course Registration Process:

- **Streamlining Registration:** Students emphasized the importance of integrating the registration process directly into the course catalogue. This would allow seamless registration and save time. Direct access and links to course pages for registration would simplify the process.
- **Enhanced Search and Filtering:** Coordinators recommended adding advanced filtering options, such as sorting by course type, instructor, schedule, and location. Including department information for each course would further improve clarity and help students make better-informed decisions.

6. User Experience Enhancements:

- **Simplification and Intuitiveness:** Both students and coordinators suggested that simplifying the interface and enhancing its intuitiveness would improve the overall user experience. Features like notifications, multimedia content, and virtual assistants were recommended to keep students informed and engaged throughout the registration process.
- **Integration of Modern Features:** Incorporating modern technologies and improving overall user-friendliness were recurring themes, with an emphasis on creating a streamlined, efficient, and user-centric course registration experience.

7. Feedback and Areas for Growth:

- **Positive Feedback and Suggested Improvements:** While students are generally satisfied with the current system, both students and coordinators see opportunities for improvement, particularly in terms of enhancing features, mobile-friendliness, and integrating modern technologies to better support Erasmus students and other users.

These findings suggest that while the University of Maribor's current course catalogue system is functional, significant improvements could be made to enhance accessibility, user experience, and functionality, especially for international students and Erasmus participants.

5. Recommendations

5.1. General Recommendations for Course Catalog Improvements

To address the diverse challenges identified across partner universities, the following general recommendations can enhance the usability, accessibility, and functionality of course catalogs:

1. **Standardization Across Institutions.** A unified structure for organizing course information should be implemented to ensure consistency. This includes standardizing categories like course title, study field, level of study (Bachelor, Master, Ph.D.), language of instruction, ECTS credits, and prerequisites. Clear indications of Erasmus+ eligibility and availability of interdisciplinary courses should also be prioritized.
2. **Detailed and Transparent Course Descriptions.** Course catalogs should include comprehensive details about each course, such as specific learning outcomes, assessment methods, teaching methods, and recommended literature. A breakdown of course goals, skills to be acquired, and expected achievements will empower students to make informed decisions.
3. **Enhanced Search and Filtering Options.** Advanced search functionalities that allow filtering by language of instruction, study level, faculty, and semester should be implemented. Interactive features like keyword-based searches and customizable dashboards can improve navigation.
4. **User-Friendly and Accessible Design.** Course catalogs should feature an intuitive interface that is accessible on all devices, including smartphones and tablets. Mobile-friendliness is critical, with designs that adapt seamlessly to different screen sizes. Compatibility with assistive technologies should be prioritized to ensure inclusivity.
5. **Regular Updates and Transparency.** Institutions should establish clear protocols for regularly updating course information. Including a visible timestamp for the last revision and enabling users to flag outdated or incorrect data would enhance reliability. Linking to dynamic faculty pages for real-time updates can further ensure accuracy.
6. **Integration with Mobility Tools.** To streamline the mobility process, CCs should integrate with platforms such as the Erasmus Without Paper (EWP) network and Online Learning Agreements (OLA). This integration would allow students to browse courses and finalize agreements within a unified system.
7. **Inclusion of Multimedia Content.** Incorporating visuals, videos, and interactive features like virtual campus tours can enrich the user experience. These elements are particularly beneficial for courses with practical components, providing a clearer understanding of their scope and requirements.

5.2 Suggestions for the Broader Mobility System

1. **Standardized Course Catalog Templates.** Mobility frameworks should encourage or mandate a standardized template for course catalogs across participating institutions. This would promote consistency, reduce confusion, and improve comparability for mobility students.
2. **Centralized Mobility Platforms.** A unified platform that aggregates course catalogs from various universities and integrates with the Erasmus+ network would streamline the selection process. This platform could provide a single point of access for students to explore courses, review credit transfer policies, and finalize agreements.
3. **Enhanced Support for Multilingual Access.** To accommodate the diverse linguistic needs of international students, mobility systems should ensure that all course descriptions are available in English alongside the local language. Support for additional languages would further enhance inclusivity.
4. **Real-Time Updates Across Institutions.** Establishing a protocol for synchronizing course catalogs with institutional databases in real time would ensure that students have access to the latest information. Cloud-based systems could facilitate this synchronization while maintaining security and data integrity.
5. **Feedback Mechanisms for Continuous Improvement.** A shared platform for collecting user feedback on course catalogs could help identify common issues and inform future enhancements. This feedback loop should be integrated into the broader mobility system to support data-driven improvements.

By addressing these recommendations, universities and mobility systems can create robust, user-friendly course catalogs that meet the diverse needs of students, coordinators, and administrators, fostering a smoother and more efficient academic mobility experience.

6. Conclusion

6.1. Summary of Findings

The review of course catalogs across partner universities highlighted significant challenges and opportunities for improvement, with several key themes emerging. One of the most pressing issues is the lack of standardization in structure, content, and functionality, which forces students to navigate inconsistent and often cumbersome systems. These inconsistencies complicate the process of course selection and reduce overall usability, with many students reporting frustration due to limited filtering options and fragmented information.

Another major challenge is the accuracy and currency of the information provided. Course catalogs frequently contain outdated or incomplete details about courses, prerequisites, or enrollment conditions. This creates uncertainty for students, particularly those planning

international mobility, as they must often rely on incomplete or prior-year information to make critical decisions.

Despite these challenges, the project identified a range of positive aspects and functional features in some systems, including efforts to integrate course registration, provide multilingual support, and enhance accessibility through mobile-friendly designs. However, these strengths are not evenly distributed across all institutions, emphasizing the need for broader systemic changes to ensure a more consistent and user-friendly experience for all students.

6.2. Future Steps and Project Impact

Moving forward, the findings from this project will serve as a foundation for implementing targeted improvements to course catalogs, both within individual institutions and at a broader, systemic level. Institutions should prioritize the harmonization of their course catalogs, ensuring that the presentation of information follows a clear and standardized format. This would enhance comparability across universities and reduce barriers for mobility students.

Efforts should also focus on integrating modern technologies, such as AI-driven assistants and interactive multimedia content, to improve user engagement and simplify navigation. Regular updates to course information, supported by automated systems and coordinated timelines, will be essential to maintaining accuracy and reliability.

At the systemic level, the insights gained from this project underscore the need for collaborative action among higher education institutions, mobility programs, and policymakers. Developing shared standards for course catalogs and investing in interoperable platforms can significantly enhance the mobility experience. Furthermore, the emphasis on multilingual support, transparent grading systems, and comprehensive course descriptions reflects the broader goal of fostering inclusivity and equity in international education.

The impact of these improvements will extend beyond individual users, contributing to a more streamlined and efficient mobility ecosystem. By addressing these challenges and building on identified strengths, the project will play a pivotal role in enhancing the quality and accessibility of international student experiences, ultimately advancing the goals of global higher education.